

Kalinka Anchova

"Medical Anthropology", Institute of Ethnology and
Folklore Studies with Ethnographic Museum,
Bulgarian Academy of Sciences
[kalinaan@abv.bg]

To Walk Again? The Children's Sanatorium in Momin Prohod for the Rehabilitation of Children with Poliomyelitis¹

Abstract: *In the Bulgarian context of child healthcare and socialist health policy, this study focuses on the Children's Sanatorium in Momin Prohod, which was dedicated to the rehabilitation of children with long-term disabilities resulting from poliomyelitis epidemics. Established in the early 1950s, it was the only specialized healthcare facility of its kind in Bulgaria, combining both therapeutic-rehabilitative and educational work. The sanatorium gained international recognition and even treated patients from abroad, including from countries on the other side of the 'Iron Curtain'. Institutionally-focused in nature, this research is situated within the dominant medical model of the time. Chronologically, it spans the 1950s and 1960s, and is based on official documents from state archives.*

Keywords: *epidemic; poliomyelitis; Momin Prohod; children's sanatorium; disabilities; rehabilitation.*

In an attempt to make sense of global experiences engendered by the major poliomyelitis epidemics of the 20th century, more and more humanitarians in recent decades have been directing their attention to national histories of poliomyelitis, offering a variety of interdisciplinary approaches and perspectives to this once primarily medical problem. The rich Anglo-Saxon, especially American tradition of such studies (Sass, Gottfried, Sorem 1996; Oshinsky 2005; Shell 2005; Silver and Wilson 2007; Offit 2007; Hecht, 2009) also includes research on Eastern European countries (Vargha 2018).

This article is largely provoked and motivated by such studies. It focuses on the "legacy" of the poliomyelitis epidemics, which left behind

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crippled children's bodies (and fates), as well as on Bulgarian health policy aimed at minimizing the damage. It is zooming in on the only specialized health institution in Bulgaria for the recovery and rehabilitation of children with permanent disabilities acquired from poliomyelitis – the Children's Sanatorium in Momin Prohod.

Once enjoying a very good reputation not only in Bulgaria but also abroad, today the signs of memory of the sanatorium's "identity" are fading. In 2005, the diplomat, writer, and translator Kiryak Tsonev bitterly observed in his memoirs: "Today this prestigious international medical facility, which brought thousands of dollars to the country, is in complete ruin, if not non-existent!" (Tsonev 2005). Few of the direct participants and witnesses of the sanatorium's life – medical and other staff, patients, or just local residents – are alive, and memories have faded. The remaining information sources are scattered and rare. In reviews of the development of Bulgarian health resort management, the sanatorium is only mentioned in passing (Chalakov 2009; Kostadinov, Karakolev 1983; Karakolev 1994). Its presence is also modest in popular science literature on Momin Prohod and Kostenets as balneological centers (Kochankov 1977; Garvanov 1965; Stoykov, Dzhelapov 1957) and/or tourist destinations (Chervenkov 1983), as the focus there is different. It seems that local historian Miho Chervenkov, in volume 3 of his extensive research on Kostenets and its valley, is among the very few who pay special attention to it (Chervenkov 2013, 173-176).

The laconic character of the sanatorium's historical narrative is another reason to choose it as a topic. Institutional in nature, the current study is situated in the leading – medicalising – model of the time. It only episodically and rather illustratively features personal stories or biographical notes about the people referred to, for convenience, as patients and staff. Chronologically, it mainly concerns the fifth and sixth decades of the past century when the sanatorium was aimed for children with residual disabilities from poliomyelitis. The study is based on the preserved institutional and party documents from and about the health institution – reports, accounts, protocols, orders, and others, usually addressed to or received from "above." Subject to the logic and philosophy of medical-clinical practice, they focus on dealing with the primary health problem, with patients playing the classic "role" of "objects" of therapy. The dialogue between the two sides in the treatment and recovery process, together with the layers of subjective perceptions and experiences of the ill children separated from their families and loved ones children, as well as

the perspectives of the parents are all missing from the purview of the administrative-medical documentation.

Brief Background

Accompanying much of human history, the poliovirus has survived quietly and undisturbed over the centuries as an endemic pathogen. However, in the early 20th century, which saw rapid industrialization, urbanization, and population density, outbreaks became more frequent and affected more and more people worldwide. The first major epidemics appeared in Europe and America, quickly gaining momentum and peaking between the 1950s and 1960s.

Poliomyelitis is not considered to be among the deadliest diseases. However, once it enters the bloodstream and from there the central nervous system, the virus destroys motor neurons, leading to the sudden restriction or loss of movements and reflexes, as well as muscle weakness and acute asymmetrical paralysis in one, several, or all limbs, most commonly affecting the legs (Tanev 1959; Bratovanov, Gabev, Kuzmov 1974: 392-400; Bozhinov 1978: 261-269). Orthopedists have called it the "virtuoso of deformities". It leaves about 40% of affected individuals disabled with varying degrees of chronic bodily damage and lost or impaired motor functions. Most affected tend to be children from 6 months to 4-5 years old. In everyday language, the disease is known as 'infantile paralysis'. Although less frequently, epidemic waves can affect other age groups – children over 5 years, adolescents, and even adults.

In many of the most affected countries, health facilities and rehabilitation centers specializing in poliomyelitis were established aiming to restore the virus-affected atrophied neuromuscular system, to prevent subsequent bone and joint deformities and contractures, to build and develop compensatory mechanisms to take over impaired or missing functions, and to physically strengthen affected individuals. These centers combined modern medical achievements with age-old natural healing methods². In the USA, for example, President Franklin Roosevelt, who underwent long-term poliomyelitis treatment in Warm Springs, Georgia, purchased about 500 hectares of land nearby in 1926 and founded the first modern rehabilitation institute specifically for the recovery of pa-

² In ancient Egypt, they applied mud from the Nile River to relieve joint pain, while the Romans used to say 'Sanitas Per Aquam' ('health through water') and extensively used the healing properties of mineral springs.

tients with the disease³ (Popov 2021). In Europe, the pioneer was Czechoslovakia, known for its mineral waters, long traditions, and school on medical rehabilitation. It has been the first on the old continent to turn in 1935 the Janske Lazne resort into a center for treating the long-term effects of poliomyelitis, using the natural resources of radioactive mineral thermal springs with properties similar to those in Warm Springs. From 1947, the USSR began building a network of poliomyelitis sanatoriums in the balneological resorts of Saki, Evpatoria, Odessa, Pyatigorsk, and others (Alexandrov, Badylkes, Bykhovsky, et al. 1958).

Bulgaria's path to creating such a specialized health institution was uneven. During the first significant spread of poliomyelitis in 1941, affecting about 70 counties with 471 registered cases (Rangelova 1963), the Main Directorate of Public Health considered an "important health and social task" not only the prevention of the disease but also the comprehensive medical care for already paralyzed individuals. On August 14, 1942, the head of the infectious diseases department at the Directorate, Dr. Hristo Danov, noted that they needed long-term, systematic "electro and hydrotherapy, X-ray therapy, and orthopaedics," which state hospitals could not provide. Only the Children's Clinic at Aleksandrovska Hospital treated poliomyelitis patients in their chronic stage, but its capacity was limited (to about 10 people) and so could not meet needs. His proposal was to establish a specialized hospital in a central location—Sofia, which offers 'the best amenities.' He also suggested considering the use of the state-owned mineral bath 'Ovcha Kupel' during off-peak times as a possible option. It had hydrotherapy, and electro and mechanotherapy devices, and it could rely on the Sofia State Level I Hospital or the university surgical clinics for X-ray therapy and orthopaedic specialists. He argued that with such an organization, about 150 patients would undergo specialised systematic treatment.⁴

The prospect of opening a hospital met with disapproval from the "Society for the Improvement and Elevation of the Ovcha Kupel Resort" and the neighborhood residents who argued it would be a "big mistake." Behind the concern for the resort was panic and fear of the disease: "Just the name 'Infantile Paralysis' painfully and frightfully tightens every parent's heart, let alone the existence of a hospital for such children... Is there no other place in our country for such a hospital, that it is necessary to open it here, in such proximity to the city with its densely populated

³ Central State Archive, fond 1305K, inventory 1, file 77, p. 62.

⁴ CSA, f. 372K, inventory 1, file 2228, pp. 1-2.

neighborhoods?"⁵ Judging by the preserved indirect traces in the archives, it seems that the hospital did exist for a short time.⁶

After this first compromise solution, the problem remained. In early 1945, the director of the University Children's Clinic, Prof. Dr. Vladimir Alexiev, also raised the issue of "special comprehensive balneological, physical, and orthopaedic treatment" for children transitioning from the acute to the paralytic stage of the disease, which the clinic could not provide, thus depriving the patients of the opportunity to get improvement at the most favourable time for them. He appealed for the creation of a "special institute for such children with specially trained staff for the purpose". During the next epidemic wave in 1947, at a conference convened by the Ministry of People's Health, leaders and medical specialists again insisted on setting up a hospital for chronically ill patients, "where comprehensive treatment could be carried out".⁷ Meanwhile, parents seeking a cure continued to wander between modern and traditional folk medicine, between hospitals and doctors, and healers, charmers, and folk orthopedists – or 'chakraks'⁸.

From 1948, there seemed to be some movement, with health authorities planning to open a "hospital-shelter" for those who had suffered from the disease. A year later, the intentions took on a more concrete shape, and the planned hospital began to be referred to as a hospital for "physically disabled children – Sofia and Bankya," which was to include "children suffering long-term effects of infantile paralysis", and which would provide comprehensive orthopaedic-surgical and physiotherapeutic treatment. However, an orthopaedic-surgical department failed to be established, and patients continued to rely on the university orthopaedic and trauma clinics. At the end of 1950, only a physiotherapy department with 50 beds was established. Over the course of nine months, 234 children were treated on an outpatient basis, with 153 undergoing inpatient care, and 53 registered as bedridden patients who had suffered from polio. The primary therapies used were hydrotherapy using mineral water from Bankya, and 'mechanotherapy' – therapeutic exercise and massage.⁹

The increasingly more frequent waves of polio in 1951, 1954, and 1957 (Rangelova 1963) occurred during a period of radical reform and

⁵ CSA, fond 372K, inventory 1, file 2230, p. 15.

⁶ CSA, fond 160, inventory 13, file 135, p. 135.

⁷ CSA, fond 160, inventory 21, file 25, pp. 1-4.

⁸ CSA, fond 160, inventory 13, file 135, pp. 141, 162.

⁹ *Ibid.*, pp. 135-139.

socialist restructuring of the healthcare system (Popov 2009; Angelova 2021). These outbreaks threatened to undermine the Fatherland Front government's declared priority of child protection – combating child mortality, effective measures against childhood and all infectious diseases, and special care for adolescents, among others (Apostolov 1981, 132). The issue of establishing a specialized health facility for rehabilitating disabled children, repeatedly emphasized by medical professionals, became increasingly urgent and required a swift, radical, comprehensive, and sustainable solution. The health authorities chose Momin Prohod.

Why Momin Prohod?

Nature has been generous to Momin Prohod, nestled in the slopes of the Sredna Gora mountain range – with its south-facing exposure, proximity to the Rila massif with a fresh influx of clean mountain air, mild climate, and beautiful views of the Rila and Rhodope mountains. But its greatest treasure is the numerous warm and medicinal mineral springs, known since ancient times. Wounded and ill soldiers from the Roman legions found healing here. During the Ottoman rule, it was known as Solu-Dervent (Water Pass or Passage of the Waters), and its name is told in many legends related to the abundance of mineral waters and their healing properties.

The first detailed description of the mineral springs in Momin Prohod was offered by Herman Skorpil in his work "Natural Resources of the Whole of Bulgaria" (1884). Since 1900, the physicochemical composition of the water from the nine springs has been examined multiple times. The results characterize it as hyperthermal (56-64°C), highly radon-rich, moderately mineralized, of sulfate-bicarbonate, sodium, fluorine, and silicon content. It has anti-allergic, anti-inflammatory, immunoprotective, and general strengthening effects, and supports the treatment of a wide range of conditions including disorders of the musculoskeletal system, respiratory system, cardiovascular system, nervous system, digestive system, skin conditions, and more.

After World War I, the healing waters revitalized the area. Authorities capped the mineral springs and erected a solid bathhouse with a pool, an inhalatorium with a dispersion system and inhalation devices, and in 1933, a new spa was built with separate sections for men and women, complete with pools and baths, and with a fountain for drinking water treatment at the front (Chalkov 2009: 220; Kochankov 1977: 20-23).

Attracted by the area's natural resources and good railway connection, from the 1920s, politicians, ministers, wealthy merchants, industri-

alists, architects, doctors, lawyers, and others began building private villas for personal use and recreation or guesthouses to rent out. Villa "Switzerland," owned by a Bulgarian diplomat, impressed visitors greatly: "The furnishings in its 26 rooms and salon are excellent and make one feel at home. Each room has running mineral water. Baths can be taken in the very radioactive mineral water. The villa has electric lighting, radio, telephone, garden, and garage. In a word, Villa 'Switzerland' has a Western European setup: it can please even the most demanding taste" (cited in Chervenkov 2013: 85). Professional associations of administrative employees and those of teachers also acquired vacation sites in the area. Carriages transported new vacationers from the country and abroad to Kostinbrod station daily¹⁰ (Kochankov 1977: 23; Stoykov, Djilepov 1957: 6). During the interwar period, Momin Prohod grew into a modern well-organized health resort.

After September 9, 1944, Momin Prohod followed the path of socialism's emerging modernization. Healthcare and resort management were taken over by the centralized state administration. In 1948, a Resort Directorate was established within the Ministry of Health, renamed to 'Sanatorium and Resort Management' (SRM) two years later. The large private villas and guest houses were nationalized and repurposed as vacation accommodation for workers. The state invested heavily in developing the resort. The Ministry of Health, the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the Central Council of the Bulgarian Trade Union, the Central Cooperative Union, working peasants, and others acquired access to sanatoriums and vacation bases (Kochankov 1977: 24; Stoykov, Djilepov 1957: 6-7). Contemporary chroniclers of Momin Prohod claim: "It changed and improved the most under the people's government".¹¹ In 1950, it was declared a spa resort of national significance.

Momin Prohod's reputation and its healing springs, its infrastructure and its proximity to Sofia and Plovdiv whilst being at a sufficient distance away from large urban centers, were likely among the reasons for its development into Bulgaria's center for the rehabilitation of children suffering from long-term effects of polio. In this context, the weighty endorsement of Professor Mikhail Petrovich Chumakov, Director of the Virology Institute in Moscow, who visited Bulgaria in the autumn of 1951 to provide urgent assistance in combating polio (Anchova 2023: 162-163), was significant. He "recommended establishing a sana-

¹⁰ State Archive – Sofia, fond 4199, inventory 1, file 17, p. 4.

¹¹ *Ibid.*, p. 4.

torium here (in Momin Prohod – editor's note) for treating children with polio".¹² At the time the USSR, and specifically Pyatigorsk had acquired some experience using radon waters to alleviate the suffering of those affected by the disease.

The children's sanatorium – from initial steps to becoming a "leading center in the country for treating the aftereffects in children who have recovered from poliomyelitis"

The sources informing us of the year of the sanatorium's establishment are indirect¹³, and the authors diverge. Some refer to 1952 – 1953, while others point to 1955 – 1957 (Kochankov 1977, 24; Chalakov 2009: 220; Chervenkov 2013: 174; Kostadinov, Karakolev 1983: 77). Each claim has its own basis in the stages of its organizational development. In 1952, the building of a large modern four-story sanatorium for adults attached to the Sanatorium and Health Resort Directorate (SHRD) was completed. A year later, a children's department was attached to it, housed in a villa with 30 beds. This could be considered the first step towards the creation of the Children's Sanatorium. Because of high demand it quickly expanded, and by 1954 it occupied additional villas and increased its capacity to 110 beds (Chervenkov 2013: 174). What was to become a separate medical institution started its life on a pavilion principle, using villas owned by the Education Union before September 9, 1944. Initially, it relied mainly on medical treatment, balneology, and physiotherapy. In 1955, a surgical-orthopedic department was established, for which the nationalized villa "Switzerland" was provided the following year.¹⁴ Pressed by the most severe epidemic in 1957, with 1065 infected people from 476 settlements nationwide (Rangelova 1963), the Ministry of People's Health and Social Care developed a comprehensive package of measures to overcome the crisis and its consequences (Anchova 2023: 163). That same year, it was decided to close the sanatorium for adults and repurpose the large building for children with poliomyelitis disabilities. The Children's Sanatorium was finally set up and legitimized as a medical institution, and its bed capacity increased several times, accommodating 310 children in winter and 360 in summer.¹⁵

¹² Ibid., p. 5.

¹³ See CSA, fond 160, inventory 19, file 148, p. 1; SA-Sofia, fond 4199, inventory 1, file 17, p. 5.

¹⁴ SA – Sofia, fond 4199, inventory 1, file 17, p. 5.

¹⁵ CSA, fond 160, inventory 19, file 148, p. 1.

The health authorities acted decisively. The sanatorium was attributed key significance, and the state mobilized significant material, personnel, and financial resources for it. The goal was set for it to become the "leading center in the country for treating the long-term effects in children who have recovered from poliomyelitis"¹⁶ and to ensure their long-term rehabilitation therapy.

The three established departments – admission & isolation (the so-called filter), physiotherapy, and surgical-orthopedic – covered the necessary range of outpatient treatment (medical, balneological, orthopedic, physical therapy, etc.), while numerous auxiliary units supported the administrative and economic activities. The order and overall organization of work were regulated. The treatment period was fixed at 100 days, but it could be extended. Upon admission, the children were placed in the filter to isolate them from the external environment and prevent the introduction of other potential contagion and infections. Here, the children adapt to the sanatorium regime, undergo functional and clinical tests, and receive an individualized treatment plan tailored to their age and the severity of their conditions. The initial procedures include mineral baths, massages, physical therapy (PT), and orthopedic prophylaxis. After the isolation period, the children are transferred to the physiotherapy and/or orthopedic departments, where the therapy is fully implemented.¹⁷

The early years of the sanatorium were marked by numerous problems, disorganization, and shortcomings. The former private villas were clearly not functionally adapted for a medical facility. Even the large sanatorium for adults did not meet the specific needs of children with mobility impairments, and the lack of an elevator further complicated their movement between floors. Poorly maintained medical records and patient logs hindered the execution of bed-day plans, resulting in either a shortage or surplus of beds, but overall, average occupancy is about 80%.¹⁸

There was "a certain level of inexperience and mistakes in medical care and child supervision during the initial period, due to the rapid conversion of the sanatorium into a children's facility with unprepared and insufficient staff."¹⁹ The sanatorium was understaffed, and medical specialists were overburdened. One doctor was responsible for 40-50 hospi-

¹⁶ SA – Sofia, fond 1697, inventory 1, file 8, p. 21.

¹⁷ CSA, fond 160, inventory 19, file 148, pp. 4-5.

¹⁸ CSA, fond 160, inventory 19, file 148, pp. 2, 6.

¹⁹ Ibid., pp. 1-2, 11-12.

tal beds, three nurses for 50 beds, and one massage therapist and one PT specialist for 30 and 50 children respectively.

The Children's Sanatorium in Momin Prohod, 1972²⁰

This workload impacted the treatment process and individual care for the patients. The staffing standard did not account for the sanatorium's patient demographic – children with severe deformities, a third of whom were nearly immobile and/or very young and unable to care for themselves. The qualifications of doctors, nurses, orderlies, and other staff were inadequate. Most of them were holdovers from the adult sanatorium and had to "suddenly become pediatricians, nurses, and child caregivers". The workload, harsh working conditions, and low pay led to high turnover. Within a single year, the sanatorium changed several chief physicians – Dr. Raiko Popov, Dr. Stoyko Kravaev, and Dr. A. Dobrev.²¹

In terms of medical activities, a study of the medical histories of 700 children in 1956 revealed the following: 201 children (28.71%) were discharged from the sanatorium with significant improvements in all neurological status indicators, 273 children (39%) showed slight improve-

²⁰ Source: CSA, coll. 720, inv. 5, a.u. 17(10), inv. № 57/2592-1.

²¹ Ibid., pp. 5-6.

ments, and 226 children (32.29%) showed no response to treatment. Clinical observations indicated that the results of balneotherapy, physiotherapy, and surgery were better when conducted during the early recovery period.²²

While the work of the surgical and orthopedic departments was rated as excellent, the balneotherapy and physiotherapy departments required modern equipment and the adoption of innovative methods gaining traction abroad. Self-taught Australian christian nurse Elizabeth Kenny (1880 – 1952) prescribed hot, moist compresses followed by gentle movements and exercises to strengthen unaffected muscle fibers and encourage surviving nerve cells. Her approach, known as "Kenny therapy," became the foundation for treating paralytic poliomyelitis and for physiotherapy in the mid-1950s. Czech physiotherapist Vladimir Janda (1928-2002), who had himself recovered from poliomyelitis, introduced a new method for testing muscle function (See Riazková 2013). To master and adopt these and other modern medical approaches, it was recommended to deepen cooperation with leading sanatoriums in Czechoslovakia and the USSR²³ as the most direct and accessible channels for new developments. There was also an urgent need for an in-house orthopedic workshop for splints, light plastic braces, and orthopedic shoes, without which motor deficits would worsen, and therapy would be in vain.²⁴

"The Great Leap"

In the context of increasingly active state policies against poliomyelitis epidemics (Anchova 2023: 163), health authorities undertook vigorous actions to improve the functioning and organisational structure of the sanatorium. From 1958, staffing standards were in place for 14 doctors, 42 nurses, 14 masseurs, 8 therapeutic exercise instructors, 98 orderlies-nannies, 8 educators, plus auxiliary staff (Chervenkov 2013: 175). A new chief physician, Dr. Dimitar Hristov Petrunov, a long-time doctor with professional experience and organizational skills who was also well-positioned politically as a former political prisoner before September 9, 1944, was appointed. In 1959, the Ministry of People's Health and Social Care strictly prohibited the admission of patients with other illnesses and

²² Ibid., pp. 3, 7.

²³ Ibid., pp. 11-12.

²⁴ Ibid., pp. 3, 7.

mandated, "only children who have recovered from poliomyelitis are to be admitted."²⁵

Under Dr. Petrunov's leadership, the sanatorium was "better organized," with staff and party office feedback describing him as a "good leader and educator"²⁶ who "enjoys a good reputation."²⁷ The documentation for those needing treatment began to be standardized, and over 3,000 registered children were systematically called for check-ups or admission (Petrunov, Ivanova 1964: 79). The bed capacity stabilized at 260, and with a total staff of 247²⁸, the sanatorium presented a much more convincing image. Most of the doctors in the departments had medical specializations and experience in their fields, with external consultants called in when necessary. The chronic shortage of masseurs, instructors, and rehabilitators was partially overcome by retraining nurses. Orderlies learned on the job how to work with children. Some of the villas were repaired and renovated.

Measures were also taken to improve medical treatments. In 1961, the chief physician of a similar sanatorium in the Czech resort of Janské Lázně and the head of their therapeutic exercise instructors arrived for a 45-day exchange in Momin Prohod. They demonstrated Sister Kenny's method, impressing the Bulgarian colleagues with the precise handling of affected muscles and the perfect technique of therapeutic procedures, combined with individualized work with recovered patients (Ivanova 1960: 124-125). "Our team learned many new things from them. Particularly valuable was their attitude toward the sick child, their planning, and targeted work".²⁹ Soon after, "Kenny therapy" was introduced and added to the traditional range of procedures, including underwater gymnastics and massage, mud applications, manual massage, therapeutic exercise, physiotherapy with electrotherapy, and surgical interventions. In 1964, a therapeutic instructor was sent to Czechoslovakia for a three-month qualification³⁰, launching the adoption of theoretical principles and elements of the methods of Herman Kabat, Karel and Berta Bobath, as well as Václav Vojta, which focus on "unlocking" hidden, unmobilized functional potential by activating muscle tone and movements (See Ryazkova 2013). A much-needed orthopedic shoe and device workshop was set up.

²⁵ SA – Sofia, fond 1697, inventory 1, file 8, pp. 20, 21.

²⁶ SA – Sofia, fond 4199, inventory 1, file 8, pp. 5, 13.

²⁷ SA – Sofia, fond 678B, inventory 1, file 8, p. 51.

²⁸ SA – Sofia, fond 1663, inventory 1, file 8, pp. 47, 83.

²⁹ SA – Sofia, fond 678B, inventory 2, file 1, p. 52.

³⁰ SA – Sofia, fond 678B, inventory 2, file 2, p. 19.

From the early 1960s, crutches began to be widely used, protecting children from worsening deformities and teaching them a more correct way of walking or creating additional compensatory possibilities. New equipment for underwater massage and other devices for mobilizing and treating damaged limbs was acquired. A new drug *Nivalin*³¹ was acquired too, after being discovered by Bulgarian pharmacologist Dr. Dimitar Paskov, as it was found to be very effective in improving motor function in paralytic poliomyelitis and gained international recognition. From 1961, a 20-day summer health retreat in the seaside sanatorium in Tuzlata near Balchik was provided, initially for 150 patients and by 1965 for about 350 children. The therapeutic liman mud from the saline seaside lake, combined with sea and sun treatments, games, and entertainment, positively affected the children's mobility and psycho-emotional state³², and the resort regime allowed for the expression of their spontaneous volitional activity (Petrunov, Ivanova 1964: 74-75).

In 1961, the sanatorium hosted a national rehabilitation meeting³³ and became a partner in the developments of the Research Institute of Balneology and Physiotherapy. Clinical observations conducted in 1964-1965 on 500 children with poliomyelitis treated in Momin Prohod with modern rehabilitation methods registered good outcomes. Improvement in the trophism of the affected muscles was observed in 396 children, and in muscle function in 411. Full or partial correction of restricted mobility was achieved in 226 cases. Of the 38 patients unable to move independently, 28 began walking with aids. Only in 11 cases (2.2%) was there no change observed. The remaining 97.8% showed some improvement from the treatment. The conclusion was that the results of previously applied surgical interventions could be achieved conservatively through innovative rehabilitation methods, which should continue to be pursued.³⁴

Behind the dry, impersonal figures and percentages of the documentation lie personal stories and destinies of children who were relearning their motor skills and abilities in the sanatorium. "To lift the sick, even if on crutches or with a cane, to free them from the need to be served by another person and from a wheelchair, to make them able to self-serve and perform some socially useful work" is a long common

³¹ SA – Sofia, fond 1663, inventory 2, file 6, pp. 41, 60; file 8, pp. 12-13.

³² SA – Sofia, fond 1663, inventory 2, file 7, pp. 1-3, 11, 15; fond 678B, inventory 2, file 3, p. 15.

³³ SA – Sofia, fond 678B, inventory 2, file 1, p. 52.

³⁴ SA – Sofia, fond 678B, inventory 2, file 5, p. 38-39.

route for patients and medical staff (Petrunov, Ivanova 1964: 78). A notable case is that of I. St. from Targovishte. About him, and others like him, we read in the documents: "This completely abandoned child, brought in immobile with 6 extremely severe contractures, severely delayed in mental development, barely able to speak despite being 11 years old. Now, the same child, with removed contractures, stands up, walks freely with crutches, climbs and descends stairs, and has learned to speak correctly and intelligibly".³⁵

The multifaceted bio-psycho-social recovery process of the children extends beyond the field of medicine. The contours of their future life paths are blurred and uncertain; they will grow and develop as individuals, construct their social world, form friendships, master professions, and seek realization in the society of the healthy, while the stigma of a visibly "defective," "incapable" body will inevitably accompany them (Ivkov 2011). The health problem of the affected children will still sprout many offshoots.

First, prolonged treatment entails disruption of the normal educational process. To avoid interrupting classes, an elementary school was established at the Children's Sanatorium in Momin Prohod during the 1953/1954 school year, and medical rehabilitation began to be complemented with pedagogical rehabilitation. The school's representative Chronicle Book documents its journey. It started with 14 students taught individually and in groups by one teacher. Over the following years, with the expansion of the sanatorium's bed capacity, the number of school-age children increased. From 1957, the school gained the status of a sanatorium middle school, allowing students to complete the full course of junior and middle school education. Their number constantly varied – some arrived, while others completed their treatment and returned to continue their education in regular schools or as private students. In the 1958/1959 school year, 146 children from the elementary course and 73 from the junior high course passed through the school, and in 1960/1961, these were 153 and 58, respectively. Starting with one elementary teacher, ten years later, there were seven teachers: four with secondary pedagogical education for the elementary course and three with higher education for the upper course³⁶, covering the spectrum of general education subjects from the curricula of regular schools. To avoid hindering therapy, classes

³⁵ SA – Sofia, fond 678B, inventory 2, file 2, p. 17.

³⁶ SA – Sofia, fond 4199, inventory 1, file 17, pp. 6, 7, 9, 13.

usually took place in the afternoon, conducted in hospital rooms due to a lack of designated classrooms.

In the joint "coexistence" of the priority therapeutic-rehabilitation work with educational work, a balance was found. Chief Physician Dr. Petrunov was motivated for the school to be on par with others: "We want our school to be no less than the one outside".³⁷ The sanatorium's party organization, using the language of the time, decisively argued: "We must dispel and will dispel the opinion among parents that our school is of poor quality and that they should send their children here only in the summer".³⁸

At the end of 1963, a commission from the Ministry of Health and Social Care, the Research Institute of Balneology and Physiotherapy, and others noted the "great leap" of the sanatorium, which in many respects had become a "rehabilitation center comparable to those in the USSR, Czechoslovakia, and even Austria".³⁹ However, they did not overlook the still weak points, mainly related to the shortage of rehabilitation workers, masseurs, and instructors, and their training, as well as prosthetics, and the work of the orthopedic workshop, among others. Discussions were also held around the challenge of incorporating new and unexplored areas into the therapeutic process, such as play therapy for young children and occupational therapy for older ones, as well as activities involving music and visual arts⁴⁰ for their more comprehensive psychological, social, and physical development. Sources of pleasant emotions and experiences, these activities improved the overall psycho-motor status, stimulated motor activity, built skills for communication, interaction, orientation, and social adaptation, formed interests, and directed toward future accessible professions (Ivkov 2011; Parizov 2002). With the appointment of a music instructor and an intermediate-level technician for arts and crafts, the creation of a photo lab, and the start of woodworking activities, the sanatorium took its first difficult and tentative steps, with the recommendation that work on social and occupational rehabilitation, psychological and verbal support for patients be expanded and deepened.⁴¹

Very soon after, within a year or two, the party bureau would report: "One of the major tasks facing the team this year (1965) was to de-

³⁷ SA – Sofia, fond 1663, inventory 2, file 5, p. 25.

³⁸ SA – Sofia, fond 678B, inventory 1, file 2, p. 35.

³⁹ SA – Sofia, fond 1663, inventory 2, file 5, pp. 17-19.

⁴⁰ *Ibid.*, pp. 17-28.

⁴¹ SA – Sofia, fond 1663, inventory 2, file 5, pp. 19-21, 25-26.

velop and introduce purposeful, educational, and emotionally enriching games, clubs, exercises, competitions, and work activities for the time outside procedures and classes. The organization and implementation of these should depend on the age, type of illness, degree and location of the impairment, as well as the mental abilities of the patient. These activities were to become an integral part of the individual motor regimen and daily schedule". In order "to heal, to enhance their sense of worthiness, and to properly guide them in finding their place in life", clubs for sewing and embroidery, cooking, photography, and electronics were established.⁴² For the intellectual development of the youth, fiction literature was available in the sanatorium's library, with nearly two-thirds of its readers being children. The radio system also regularly broadcasted music, children's programs, and news bulletins from Radio Sofia.⁴³ These were the windows to the wider world awaiting them outside.

In the increasingly complex rehabilitation and social adaptation work with young patients, an important role was assigned to the educators and the educational work of the staff. The lack of maternal care, the prolonged disruption of the child-mother bond⁴⁴, and extended separation from family had additional psychological trauma. This is why, for Dr. Petrunov "Educational work among the children needs to be very good because it is our duty to leave them emotionally capable. Regarding work therapy and vocational guidance, educators should find the right approach, and the role of children's teachers should evolve into therapeutic-educational roles. They need to know the positions in which to place the child to avoid increasing contractures; such play therapy we can introduce here. We must also perform mental assessments. Other sanatoriums have psychologists, but here, the educators are the psychologists".⁴⁵ Such were the stated intentions which aimed to compensate for and fill the emotional vacuum created by the enforced isolation from the family environment.

For the future professional realization of the children, a social worker was appointed to assist in organizing vocational guidance towards special technical schools, schools, and crafts for patients who have completed their treatment. According to their abilities and interests, with the sanatorium's mediation with the Ministry of People's Education, many

⁴² SA – Sofia, fond 678B, inventory 2, file 3, pp. 12, 14-15.

⁴³ SA – Sofia, fond 678B, inventory 2, file 2, p. 28; file 3, pp. 21, 26.

⁴⁴ From the reviewed documentation, it could not be determined whether mothers were allowed as companions and if so, in which cases.

⁴⁵ SA – Sofia, fond 678B, inventory 2, file 2, p. 41.

students from the 7th and 8th grades were accepted to continue their secondary education in reputable educational institutions – economic technical schools, radio and television technical schools, chemistry technical schools, language high schools, and more.⁴⁶

Care was also taken for the proper ideological and political education of the youth as citizens of the new socialist society. In alignment with the social environment, they were included in the framework of mass youth organizations. First, for children between 9 and 14 years old, the Dimitrov Pioneer Organization “September” was created, followed by the Dimitrov Communist Youth Union organization for the older ones. Significant dates and official holidays were solemnly celebrated, lectures and artistic programs were given, and the celebration of September 9th was accompanied by a pioneer bonfire.⁴⁷ In solidarity with their patients even after treatment, a meeting was held on May 16, 1960, at the Pioneer Palace in Sofia.⁴⁸

In the ideologically and politically divided world of the Cold War, the sanatorium was a typical socialist health institution of a small country with limited resources from the Eastern Bloc. Inevitably subject to the prevailing political practices and ideologies, it followed congress decisions and directives, built party and other accompanying satellite organizational structures, participated in socialist competition, and propagated the advantages of the socialist model. However, beyond doctrinaire principles, encouraging results were achieved in restorative therapy.

The "domestic" account of the administrative-medical documentation for the progressive development of the Children's Sanatorium in Momin Prohod is confirmed internationally. Having fulfilled the state mandate to "become the leading center in the country for the treatment of the long-term effects in children who had polio"⁴⁹ and having established itself as the only first-class medical facility on the Balkan Peninsula with such a specialized profile (Cherenkov 2013: 176), it attracted patients from abroad. Authorities "from above" opened the sanatorium's doors to them usually for payment to the state budget in hard currency.⁵⁰

⁴⁶ SA – Sofia, fond 678B, inventory 2, file 3, pp. 15-16; fond 1663, inventory 2, file 6, p. 124.

⁴⁷ SA – Sofia, fond 4199, inventory 1, file 17, pp. 7, 10, 15, and others.

⁴⁸ SA – Sofia, fond 1663, inventory 2, file 5, p. 9.

⁴⁹ SA – Sofia, fond 1697, inventory 1, file 8, p. 21.

⁵⁰ CSA, fond 882, inventory 2, file 416, p. 4.

The earliest fragmentary information is from 1959-1960 about two children from Romania.⁵¹ A much clearer picture of the international prestige and interest in the sanatorium is given by the preserved lists of children admitted between 1961 – 1965 and 1967 from different parts of the world. The numerical expression over the years is: 1961/1962 – 19; 1963 – 36; 1964 – 50; 1965 – 56; and 1967 noted a several-fold increase reaching a peak of 131 foreign patients (likely data combined with 1966). Many of the entries indicate second, third, or fourth admissions.⁵²

The geographical spread is interesting. Patients predominantly came from neighboring Balkan countries, mostly from Macedonia, followed by Greece, Romania, Yugoslavia, and fewer from Turkey. Others were commonly from socialist countries – Poland, Czechoslovakia, Hungary, East Germany, and the USSR. Some came from the other side of the "Iron Curtain" – Italy, West Germany, England, even the USA, and also from distant exotic destinations – Cuba, Tanzania, Ivory Coast. A notable increase in children from the Middle East was observed – mainly from Israel, Syria, Lebanon, but also Jordan, Iraq, Kuwait, sometimes numbering around 75 individuals.⁵³

The growing international popularity of the sanatorium coincided with the development in the late 1950s of the most famous Bulgarian medicine to this day which went under various names – *Nivalin*, based on an extract from the snowdrop flower. Previously used treatments for polio, such as serums, blood transfusions from parents, multivitamin products and vitamin B1, sulfa drugs, antibiotics, etc., were not particularly effective. However, the new medication showed good results in improving motor functions, offering new hopes for addressing the paralytic consequences of polio, and received wide recognition in medical circles, as well as in the foreign press, radio, and television. The Italian Communist Party's organ, "L'Unità," introduced Bulgarian discoverer Dr. Paskov to its readers in 1959, extensively covering the medication, the clinical trials conducted, noted mobility improvements, supported by specific cases, informing that in Bulgaria it was available in all pharmacies for 60 stotinki per ampoule and had already entered Belgium, France, Romania, Turkey, Germany, and others.⁵⁴ In 1961, French television made a film about the medication and Dr. D. Paskov who was invited several times to

⁵¹ CSA, fond 160, inventory 22, file 65, p. 38; file 66, p. 176.

⁵² SA – Sofia, fond 1663, inventory 2, file 6, pp. 9-16.

⁵³ *Ibid.*, pp. 9-16.

⁵⁴ *Ibid.*, pp. 9-16.

lecture at the Sorbonne. That same year, for this scientific achievement, he was awarded the prestigious international “Enyo” prize in Naples.

The cumbersome procedures for the official recognition of *Nivalin* in various countries delayed its widespread entry into foreign markets. Addressed to Dr. Paskov, the Ministry of Health, the Central Committee of the Bulgarian Communist Party, and personally to Todor Zhivkov, and to newspaper and magazine editors, dozens of letters arrived from citizens of the USSR, Poland, Hungary, Germany, Belgium, and others, requesting the medicine in order to save their children from disabilities caused by polio⁵⁵. In the spring of 1960, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs secretly informed the Central Committee that Luigi Longo, deputy to the general secretary of the Italian Communist Party, Palmiro Togliatti, had approached our embassy in Rome for the delivery of 100 ampoules for the treatment of “our comrade’s children.”⁵⁶ Again through party channels, in the same year, a visiting member of the Italian Communist Party Central Committee, Tabet, inquired: “Would our Central Committee agree to the sale of Nivalin in Italy through a party-designated company. Without publicizing it, of course, to allow the party to gain certain benefits and prevent excessive price hikes by other traders, as the base price here is already quite high, making it almost impossible for a worker or even for an average Italian citizen to afford Nivalin treatment”.⁵⁷ Proven but still inaccessible and insufficiently available to the general “consumer” abroad, the new Bulgarian medicine was already integrated as an essential element in the therapy offered by the Momin Prohod sanatorium. This also contributed to foreign interest in the health facility.

Among many foreign patients, the progress achieved through medical rehabilitation at the sanatorium was visible. A Yugoslav citizen, ill since 1955 and almost immobile, after treatment, could walk well without a brace on one leg.⁵⁸ A girl from the USA, evidently with Bulgarian roots judging by her surname came to us in a very severe condition after four years of unsuccessful treatment there. Immobile, with severe bedsores and pelvic-reservoir disorders, her condition significantly improved within 7-8 months, and she could already take 20-30 steps”.⁵⁹ The knowledgeable expert on the Arab world, Kyriak Tsonev, also added a

⁵⁵ CSA, fond 160, inventory 22, file 66, pp. 88, 93-94, 110, 139-140, 248-249; fond 1B, inventory 24, file 254, pp. 2, 3-4.

⁵⁶ CSA, fond 1B, inventory 33, file 337, pp. 1-2.

⁵⁷ *Ibid.*, pp. 3-5.

⁵⁸ DA-Sofia, fond 1663, inventory 2, file 5, p. 38.

⁵⁹ DA-Sofia, fond 678B, inventory 2, file 2, p. 18.

detail. In Syria, he said, there is an influential Atassi family from Homs, always in power, spanning from the far-right to the far-left, having given the country several presidents. In the city center, there is a pharmacy “Atassi,” naturally also belonging to the family. “Its owner Hulusi simply revered Bulgaria – thanks to treatment at the Momin Prohod children’s sanatorium specializing in polio, his completely immobile child had started walking”. (Tsonev 2005).

With the discovery of the polio vaccine and the initiation of mass immunization, epidemics, including those in Bulgaria, receded and eventually subsided. Those who had been affected during the peak decades of the mid-20th century grew up and were predominantly no longer children. From the second half of the 1960s, the Children's Sanatorium in Momin Prohod began to gradually change and lose its strict focus on poliomyelitis. The traditions and achievements established over the years, the well-developed medical infrastructure, and the accumulated professional experience were redirected towards the treatment of other socially significant childhood diseases of the central and peripheral nervous system and the musculoskeletal system. For health authorities, institutional medical care for the recovery of those affected by polio epidemics ceased to be concentrated solely on Momin Prohod. It was dispersed and taken up by other sanatoriums for children or adults with broader scopes, such as Tuzlata, Kotel, Pavel Banya, Burgas Mineral Baths, Sapareva Banya, Velingrad, Vlas, and others. The chapter on the only specialized sanatorium in our country for the rehabilitation of children with permanent disabilities acquired from polio gradually turned and closed. The focus broadened and opened to other healthcare facilities.

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